

THE MASK OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS: AN INFANT WITH VON ZUMBUSCH TYPE OF GENERALIZED PUSTULAR PSORIASIS UNDER

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Background. Generalized pustular psoriasis (GPP) is a rare and most severe form of psoriasis. The pathogenesis of GPP is not yet fully understood. However, recent research suggests that the interleukin-36 pathway plays a crucial role in its development. Infantile pustular psoriasis is uncommon and usually occurs in older children. This form of psoriasis may be masked by other diseases, for instance, topical glucocorticoid-resistant atopic dermatitis, leading to late diagnosis. As a result, there is a growing need to familiarise medical personnel with the fundamentals of differential diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of this disease.

Objective. The aim of the work was to analyse the course of generalized pustular psoriasis, also known as Zumbusch's disease, through a clinical case study.

Material and methods. A retrospective analysis of the primary medical records and personal supervision of the patient with von Zumbusch type of generalized pustular psoriasis aged 3 years was performed, evaluating data on medical history, clinical symptoms, and results of laboratory and instrumental examinations.

Results. Resistant cases of atopic dermatitis may be a sign of a more complex pathological process, such as generalized pustular psoriasis.

Conclusion. Awareness of rare diseases is essential for physicians across all specialities.

Keywords: *children, psoriasis/epidemiology, psoriasis/genetics, generalized pustular psoriasis, von Zumbusch disease, clinical signs, cytostatics, biologics.*

Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory disease that primarily affects the skin. It is currently a pressing issue not only in dermatology [1]. There are several clinical subtypes of psoriasis, including uncommon pustular forms that are further divided into localised and generalised. Localized forms comprise acrodermatitis continua of Hallopeau and palmoplantar pustular psoriasis. Acute generalized pustular psoriasis of von Zumbusch, pustular psoriasis of pregnancy, and infantile pustular psoriasis are all generalized forms of pustular psoriasis [2].

Generalized pustular psoriasis (GPP) is a rare and severe multisystem form of the disease and manifests as erythematous and edematous plaques on which multiple pustules appear, associated or not with the plaque form [3]. During the acute phase of the illness, the child's overall condition is severe, with a body temperature increase to 39-40°C and a decline in general health [9]. Typical forms of GPP are characterized by intermittent flares that can have a self-remitting course and can be interspersed with periods of partial or complete remission [4].

GPP was first described in 1910 by Leo von Zumbusch, a dermatologist from Munich. He presented a case study of a brother and sister who both suffered from the disease. The brother experienced intermittent pustular rashes on pre-existing psoriatic plaques, even when applying irritating ointments. In contrast, the sister had a sudden acute attack that became pustular in nature, which unfortunately resulted in her death [5].

Recognition of GPT as a rare disease is increasing worldwide. The global incidence of GPT is unknown, but several countries have reported its incidence and prevalence based on geographical location. It has been observed that Asians (7.46 per million in Japan) are more susceptible to the disease than Caucasians (1.76 per million in France) [6, 7]. In the pediatric population, it seems to occur more frequently in the male sex (3:2), ranging from 0.6 to 7% of psoriasis cases. The mean age of onset is between 6.6 and 7.6 years old [2].

The exact pathogenesis of GPP has not been fully understood. However, studies have identified an IL-36 receptor antagonist deficiency in patients with pustular psoriasis and patients with pustular psoriasis have also been successfully treated with a novel monoclonal antibody against the IL-36 receptor. Therefore, the interleukin-36 pathway plays a crucial role in its development [8].

The main diagnostic methods for confirming the diagnosis are punch biopsy and medical genetic testing [1, 4]. First-line drugs used for children are acitretin, cyclosporine, methotrexate, and etanercept. Second line options include systemic treatments in diffuse disease (e.g., etanercept and adalimumab) or topical treatments in localized disease (e.g., corticosteroids, calcipotriene, and tacrolimus) [9].

From the given analysis perspective, the following observed clinical case can be of interest. Patient M., born in 2019, is seen in an urban polyclinic in Russia with the diagnosis of von Zumbusch type of generalized pustular psoriasis.

The patient's family history reveals a predisposition to psoriasis, as both the patient's mother and grandfather on the mother's side have been diagnosed with the condition. This suggests a hereditary link to the development of skin diseases.

At the age of 2 months, the boy was examined for rashes in the folds of his neck, similar to prickly heat. The rash was associated with the introduction of 'Similac Gold' formula feeding. The patient has been diagnosed with atopic dermatitis and a food allergy to cow's milk. The prescription of topical glucocorticoid therapy and diet of amino acid-based milk formula did not result in any improvement. On the contrary, the rashes intensified, spread to the entire body surface, and proved to be resistant to therapy.

During the course of the disease, vesiculo-pustular elements were observed, which were initially thought of as an infectious process. Amoxicillin clavulanate was prescribed, but one day after taking antibiotics, the child has a fever to 37.7°C and he was admitted to hospital.

Despite therapy with an amino acid-based formula, antihistamines and adsorbents, severe diffuse skin lesion with infection of separate elements persisted. To confirm the diagnosis, a punch biopsy was taken from the right thigh area, resulting in a diagnosis of Von Zumbusch type of generalized pustular psoriasis. After that the patient was prescribed systemic therapy with methotrexate at a dose of 10 mg/m² once a week for at least 1.5 months.

During the four-year follow-up observation, the skin pathology exhibited an incomplete remission. Unfortunately, at the moment, the genetic variant of our clinical case has not been established.

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